

Full Length Article

Ozone nanobubble effects on early development of rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*) and rearing-water microbial communities in a flow-through hatchery

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ABSTRACT

Nanobubble technology is increasingly being explored in aquaculture for its potential to enhance water quality, control pathogens, and improve fish performance. This study investigated the effects of ozone nanobubbles (O₃NB) on rearing-water microbial communities and early development of rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*) in a pond-water-sourced flow-through hatchery system. A two-factorial experimental design combined four O₃NB water treatments (Control; Low: 277 ± 104 mV; Moderate: 392 ± 134 mV; High: 610 ± 122 mV) with two rearing techniques (with or without regular removal of unfertilised eggs and dead individuals; R and NR). O₃NB exposure altered microbial community composition in rearing water, with alpha-diversity indices (ACE, OTU, Shannon, Simpson) showing negative relationships with increasing O₃NB intensity. Taxonomic profiling indicated a marked reduction in genus richness under higher O₃NB exposure, with communities dominated by *Moheibacter*, *Tepidimonas*, and *Sphingobacterium*. Regular removal of dead organic matter increased hatching and survival compared with non-removal. O₃NB effects were dose-dependent: the highest mean larval body length and high hatching success (~80 %) occurred under Low O₃NB treatment among surviving larvae, particularly under R-technique, while Moderate and High exposures reduced hatching (<40 %) and survival (<5 % in High-NR). Yolk-sac absorption occurred more rapidly under O₃NB exposure, but was completed across all groups by 77 dpF. Overall, these findings indicate that low-level O₃NB, when used to complement (rather than replace) standard hatchery practices such as the removal of dead organic matter, can support microbial control and early developmental performance of rainbow trout in hatchery systems with elevated organic load. In contrast, excessive exposure compromises embryo viability and larval survival. Further optimisation of O₃NB dosing and application strategies is therefore required, recognising the effectiveness and safety under different system-specific conditions.

1. Introduction

Aquaculture plays a crucial role in the global food supply, providing livelihoods for millions of people and contributing significantly to sustainable nutrition worldwide [1]. Despite its importance, the sector faces persistent challenges related to water management, disease outbreaks, and sustainable intensification of production [2]. Among these challenges, effective water disinfection remains fundamental, as water conditions directly influence the health and performance of aquatic

organisms throughout their life cycle [3,4], particularly during early developmental stages, when pathogen outbreaks can severely compromise production success [5].

The embryonic and larval stages of fish represent the most vulnerable periods of ontogenetic development, during which rearing conditions strongly influence survival, growth, and performance [6]. From fertilisation to yolk-sac absorption, early development involves physiological and morphological transitions [7–9], including the establishment of respiration, digestion, and locomotion [10]. Immature defence

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mechanisms render these stages particularly susceptible to environmental stressors and pathogens [11], highlighting the importance of rearing environments that minimise stress and microbial pressure while maintaining egg quality [12]. Appropriate water treatment can reduce pathogen load, improve environmental conditions [13], and support oxygen availability, promoting optimal development and performance [14].

Conventional disinfection strategies in aquaculture include mechanical and biological filtration, chemical treatments (e.g. chlorination or peracetic acid), ultraviolet irradiation, ozonation, or combinations thereof [14–16]. While effective, these approaches often involve trade-offs between microbial control and animal tolerance [17,18], while UV-C irradiation is limited by operational costs, limited effectiveness, short lifespan, and concerns related to mercury-containing lamps [18]. Ozonation is widely recognised for its strong oxidative and disinfecting capacity; however, its application is constrained by potential formation of harmful by-products, rapid dissipation of residual activity, and risks to fish health when exposure exceeds safe thresholds [19,20].

In this context, nanobubble (NB) technology has emerged as a promising alternative water treatment approach due to its distinctive physicochemical properties. NB are ultrafine gas-filled bubbles that remain suspended in water because of their near-neutral buoyancy and high stability [21,22]. Compared with common bubbles, NB (<200 nm) offer enhanced gas transfer efficiency, larger specific surface area, increased stability, and stronger surface charge [23–25,86]. These properties have driven growing interest in nanobubble applications across engineering, wastewater treatment, and aquaculture systems [26].

Ozone nanobubbles (O₃NB) combine the oxidative strength of ozone with the physicochemical advantages of nanobubbles and have been widely reported to inactivate bacterial pathogens (e.g. *Vibrio* spp., *Aeromonas* spp.), eliminate bacteriophages, and reduce disease incidence in a range of cultured species, including jade perch (*Scortum barcoo*), Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*), and Pacific white shrimp (*Penaeus vannamei*) [27–32,86,87]. O₃NB applications have been explored across freshwater and marine aquaculture, biofloc systems, recirculating aquaculture, hydroponics, and aquaponics [24,25,30,32–36,86], with reported benefits including improved removal of organic matter and micropollutants, enhanced water clarity, and improved animal health [19,22,25,37,86].

Beyond direct pathogen suppression, O₃NB treatment can influence the composition and structure of microbial communities. Recent 16S rRNA and metagenomic studies indicate that O₃NB exposure can alter both dominant and rare microbial taxa, thereby affecting nutrient cycling, water quality, and host–microbe interactions in aquaculture environments [38,39]. While such shifts may enhance microbial turnover and suppress opportunistic pathogens [25,40,86], excessive oxidative pressure may also reduce beneficial microbial groups or promote instability in community structure, with potential consequences for ecosystem resilience and animal health [25,38,39,41,42,86]. These considerations highlight the importance of evaluating not only disinfection efficacy but also the broader ecological effects of O₃NB application.

Although ozonation has been successfully applied in hatchery practice [43–45], significant knowledge gaps remain regarding the effects of O₃NB during early fish development. In particular, limited information exists on how O₃NB exposure influences key ontogenetic processes such as hatching, yolk-sac absorption, early growth, survival, and the microbial characteristics of rearing water under different rearing conditions. Accordingly, this study aimed to address these gaps by evaluating four O₃NB water treatments (Control, Low, Moderate, High), in combination with two rearing techniques (with or without regular removal of unfertilised eggs and dead individuals), on rearing-water microbial communities and early developmental performance of rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*) in a flow-through pond-water hatchery system.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Nanobubble generation

An assembly of three generators was used to create ozone nanobubbles (O₃NB): an oxygen concentrator with a production of 2–10 L min⁻¹ at a concentration of 90 ± 3 % (OX-10A, Oxytek Medical Technology Co. Ltd., China), an ozone (O₃) generator producing 10 g O₃ h⁻¹ from dry air (ANNIHILATOR OT10, OZONTECH, s.r.o., Czech Republic), and a nanobubble (NB) generator with a maximum flow capacity of 1000 L h⁻¹ (aQua+ 075, AquaPro Solutions Pte. Ltd., Singapore; <https://www.aquapro-solutions.com/nanobubble-generator>). The first device produced oxygen (O₂, at a setting of 3 L min⁻¹). The second generator converted this oxygen into O₃. And the third device, the NB generator, subsequently created O₃NB-saturated water.

Nanoparticle tracking analysis (NTA) was employed to quantify particle size distribution and concentration in the water samples using a NanoSight NS300 instrument (Malvern Instruments Ltd., UK). This technique is based on the visualisation and tracking of Brownian motion of nanoparticles under laser illumination, providing high-resolution measurements of both particle size and concentration. Two types of water samples were analysed: untreated tap water (used as a blank control) and water subjected to ozone nanobubble (O₃NB) generation. Each sample was measured under identical conditions to ensure comparability, and size distribution was reported as percentile values (<90 %, <50 %, and <10 %), representing the particle size thresholds below which the indicated proportion of particles was found.

2.2. Experimental design

2.2.1. Experimental groups

The experiment employed a two-factor design. The first factor was the rearing technique with two levels: without removal (NR)—no manual removal—and with regular removal (R)—manual removal of unfertilised eggs and dead individuals during incubation and early rearing. The second factor was the ozonated pond water treatment (O₃NB, mV) with four levels: Control, Low, Moderate, and High. This factorial design yielded eight experimental groups—Control-NR, Control-R, Low-NR, Low-R, Moderate-NR, Moderate-R, High-NR, and High-R (Schema 1):

Control-NR / Control-R: no O₃NB treatment (192 ± 40 mV),
 Low-NR / Low-R: low O₃NB treatment (277 ± 104 mV),
 Moderate-NR / Moderate-R: moderate O₃NB treatment (392 ± 134 mV),
 High-NR / High-R: high O₃NB treatment (610 ± 122 mV).

Each experimental group was replicated in four independent aquaria (A–D). Treatments were applied continuously from egg fertilisation until yolk-sac absorption, thus encompassing both the embryonic and larval stages of rainbow trout [8].

2.2.2. Experimental system

The experimental hatchery flow-through system was supplied with pond water sourced from a 42 ha pond used for both recreational purposes and fishery production. Before entering the hatchery, the water was pre-treated using screens and sedimentation to remove coarse particles and suspended matter. The system comprised two upper reservoirs (troughs, 200 L each), one containing untreated pond water and the other O₃NB-treated pond water. Water from both reservoirs was gravity-fed to a lower trough (200 L) housing 32 plexiglass incubators (2 L each). Each incubator received a constant total inflow of 500 mL min⁻¹, supplied via two separate pipes with adjustable taps, allowing controlled mixing of untreated and O₃NB-treated pond water to establish four experimental treatments (Control, Low, Moderate, High). The system operated in a single-pass flow-through configuration, with no water recirculation. The O₃NB generation system (comprising O₂, O₃, and O₃NB generators) operated continuously for 30-minute cycles per hour

Scheme 1. Representation of the experimental design supplied with pond water divided into untreated and O₃NB-treated reservoirs, with O₃NB generated using an oxygen concentrator, ozone generator, and nanobubble generator. Water from both reservoirs was gravity-fed separately and mixed via adjustable taps to establish four O₃NB treatments (Control, Low, Moderate, High), each combined with two rearing techniques (without removal, NR; with regular removal of dead material, R), resulting in eight experimental groups (Control-NR, Control-R, Low-NR, Low-R, Moderate-NR, Moderate-R, High-NR, and High-R), each tested in four replicates (incubators A–D).

throughout the day. This setup ensured that embryos and larvae were incubated and reared under consistent conditions throughout the experiment. Photographs of the experimental system are provided in the Supplementary Materials (Suppl. 1 and 2) to facilitate visualisation of the system layout.

2.2.3. Experimental fish

Rainbow trout broodfish (two females and two males) were separately spawned into dry test tubes at a recirculation fish farm (Vladimír Šefl, Bušanovice, Czech Republic) to obtain gametes (eggs and sperm). The gametes were then transported within two hours to the fish hatchery in a polystyrene box (with sperm kept on ice) and supplied with pond water (Mydlovary, Czech Republic), where the study was conducted. A split-brood fertilisation was performed, in which the eggs from each female were divided into two containers and fertilised with milt from different males, ensuring diverse genetic combinations. At the start of the experiment, 4000 fish eggs (average weight 78.3 ± 7.6 mg; diameter 5.7 ± 0.5 mm) were fertilised and distributed across 32 rearing incubators. Four incubators were allocated to each experimental group.

2.2.4. Rearing conditions

During the experiment, the rearing and development of the fish were regularly monitored, including recording mortality. As the pond water source is influenced by weather conditions, the natural temperature in the Southern Czech Republic rose from 4.2°C to 15.5°C over the course of the experiment (March–May). Embryos and larvae were exposed to this natural pond-water temperature regime throughout the study, which was consistent across all experimental groups; therefore, any observed differences can be attributed to the O₃NB treatments rather

than variations in water source or temperature. This temperature range falls within the species' viable range limits [8,46]. Water temperature, pH, dissolved oxygen, and oxidation–reduction potential (ORP) were monitored throughout the experiment; temperature was recorded hourly using Minikin dataloggers (Environmental Measuring Systems s. r.o., Czech Republic), while pH, dissolved oxygen, and ORP were measured 2–3 times per week using a portable multimeter (HQ40d, Hach Lange GmbH, Germany). Dissolved oxygen and ORP were additionally monitored during O₃NB generator on–off cycles to characterise treatment-related fluctuations.

2.2.5. Feeding

Feeding commenced 14 days post-hatching, once all groups had initiated active foraging. From the onset of exogenous feeding, fish were supplied twice daily (09:00 and 14:00) with dry starter feed INICIO Plus G (BioMar SAS, France) at a pellet size of 0.6 mm, and offered *ad libitum* to ensure adequate intake.

2.3. Sampling and analysis

2.3.1. Microbial community characteristics of rearing water

At the end of the experiment, 500 mL water-column samples were collected in duplicate from the two upper reservoirs (untreated pond water and O₃NB-treated water) and from each of the four O₃NB treatment groups (inlet into incubators A–D) and immediately filtered through 0.22 μm filters (Techno Plastic Products AG, Switzerland). The filters were immediately frozen at -80°C and later thawed and homogenised for DNA extraction using a Qiagen kit (Germany) with a modified protocol [47]. Briefly, samples were centrifuged (5000 rpm, 5

min), treated with STE buffer (300 μL) and lysozyme (10 μL), and incubated at 37°C for 30 min. Samples were then vortexed with breaking buffer (300 μL) and phenol:chloroform:isoamyl alcohol (300 μL) for 10 min, centrifuged (11000 rpm, 5 min), and the aqueous phase (500 μL) transferred to Eppendorf tubes. DNA was precipitated with 99 % ethanol (1000 μL), centrifuged (11000 rpm, 10 min). Washed with 70 % ethanol (250 μL), centrifuged (11000 rpm, 5 min), and air-dried for 30 min.

The dried pellets were re-suspended in buffer EB (50 μL ; Qiagen, Germany), centrifuged (11000 rpm, 1 min), treated with RNase and vortexed (2 μL , 550 rpm, 37°C, 1 h), and DNA concentration ($\text{ng } \mu\text{L}^{-1}$) was measured on a NanoDrop ND-1000 spectrophotometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Inc., USA). DNA was further purified using NucleoSpin gDNA Clean-up kit (Macherey-Nagel, Germany). The V3–V4 regions of the 16S rRNA gene were amplified by using the pair-end primers [48] and sequenced on a MiSeq V2 platform (Illumina, USA; 250 bp paired-end reads). Sequencing data underwent quality control and trimming using the FastQC program. The results were further analysed using the bioinformatics platform QIIME 2 [49] to investigate microbial community characteristics.

2.3.2. Egg sampling and measurement

Egg mean weight was assessed by weighing 20 unfertilised eggs in triplicate using a Korona 79444 Anja scale (Koronaelectric GmbH, Germany). Egg mean diameter was measured from photographs taken with a USB digital microscope (Flex 66144, Reflecta GmbH, Germany) alongside a millimetre scale, with image analysis performed in ImageJ (NIH, USA). These eggs were not used in the experimental fertilisation.

2.3.3. Hatching and survival rates

Hatching and survival were monitored three times per week. Embryos, hatched larvae, and dead individuals were counted in each incubator. In the NR-technique, dead individuals remained in the incubators, whereas in the R-technique, they were removed regularly with plastic tweezers. Rates were calculated as:

$$\text{Survival rate (\%)} = \text{survivors} \times 100 / \text{initial stocked individuals}$$

$$\text{Hatching rate (\%)} = \text{hatched larvae} \times 100 / \text{initial stocked individuals}$$

2.3.4. Fish sampling and measurement

Fish were sampled weekly after hatching until the full yolk-sac absorption. Twenty individuals per group (when available) were randomly selected and anaesthetised in a eugenol bath (30 $\mu\text{L } \text{L}^{-1}$). Each fish was photographed and analysed using the same imaging procedure as for the eggs. Measurements included total body length, then yolk-sac length and depth, from which yolk-sac volume was calculated according to Blaxter & Hempel [50]:

$$\text{Yolk-sac volume} = (\pi/6) \times \text{yolk-sac length} \times \text{yolk-sac depth}^2.$$

2.4. Statistical evaluation

Experimental data were analysed in R version 4.0.3 (R Core Team, 2020) using RStudio IDE (Posit Software, PBC) and STATISTICA 12.0 (StatSoft, Inc., USA).

For statistical analysis of survival and hatching rates, the incubators were used as experimental units; whereas for statistical analysis of fish body parameters (total body length and yolk-sac volume), measured individuals were assessed. Data normality and homogeneity of variances were tested using the Shapiro-Wilk and Cochran's tests. One-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's HSD test was used to identify significant differences between groups, while two-way ANOVA assessed the effects of rearing technique (NR vs R), O₃NB concentration (Control–High), and their interaction. For data that were non-normal or exhibited unequal variances, non-parametric approaches were applied, including multiple comparison tests following Kruskal-Wallis analysis.

For microbial community analyses, the correlation between O₃NB concentration (%) and alpha-diversity indices (ACE, Observed Features, Shannon's index, and Simpson's index) was assessed using linear

regression. The diversity indices were calculated as follows: Shannon and Simpson indices were computed to quantify community diversity, incorporating both species richness and evenness; the number of OTUs was determined from clustered sequence features; and the Abundance-based Coverage Estimator (ACE) was used to estimate species richness by accounting for rare taxa. To assess beta-diversity, principal coordinates analysis (PCoA) based on Bray–Curtis dissimilarity was performed using the relative abundance of bacterial OTUs. Group differences were tested using PERMANOVA and ANOSIM. Additionally, Venn diagrams were created with Jvenn (<http://bioinfo.genotoul.fr/jvenn>) to illustrate shared and unique OTUs among groups.

A significance threshold of $P < 0.05$ was adopted for all tests, and results are presented as mean \pm SD in the figures.

3. Results

3.1. Particle size distribution and concentration

Nanoparticle tracking analysis (NTA) revealed clear differences in bubble size distribution (nm) and concentration (bubbles mL^{-1}) between untreated tap water and water subjected to O₃NB generation. The untreated tap water (blank control) contained bubbles with a mean size of 260.3 ± 23.6 nm at a concentration of $1.7e^{07} \pm 2.1e^{06}$ bubbles mL^{-1} . Within this distribution, <90 % of the bubbles were smaller than 411.2 ± 75.1 nm, <50 % were below 241.3 ± 13.9 nm, and <10 % were under 112.4 ± 11.2 nm (Fig. 1B). In contrast, the O₃NB-treated water exhibited substantially smaller bubbles, with a mean diameter of 136.2 ± 0.8 nm and a markedly higher concentration of $1.5e^{08} \pm 4.6e^{06}$ bubbles mL^{-1} . In this treatment, <90 % of the bubbles were smaller than 241.9 ± 10.6 nm, <50 % were below 111.7 ± 3.1 nm, and <10 % were under 74.7 ± 2.2 nm (Fig. 1A).

3.2. Water quality dynamics under O₃NB treatment

Throughout the experiment, pond water in the reservoir exhibited a mean temperature of 7.9 ± 2.6 °C, pH 7.6 ± 0.6 , oxygen concentration 93.6 ± 3.8 %, and ORP 214 ± 64 mV. In the O₃NB-treated reservoir water, mean temperature and pH were comparable (8.5 ± 3.2 °C and pH 7.4 ± 0.6 , respectively); however, oxygen concentration and ORP showed fluctuations associated with generator operation. During 30-minute O₃NB operating cycles, oxygen concentration increased to 199.3 ± 40.8 % and 793 ± 119 mV. Similarly, in the experimental O₃NB-treated groups, mean oxygen levels increased during generator operation, reaching 145.0 ± 39.0 % in the Low, 163.3 ± 34.9 % in the Moderate, and 192.2 ± 18.4 % in the High treatment, whereas oxygen concentration in the Control group remained stable (93.4 ± 3.1 %) and was unaffected by generator function. During the subsequent 30-minute generator off cycles, oxygen saturation declined to 119 ± 34.1 % in the Low, 114.8 ± 27.1 % in the Moderate, and 111.9 ± 31.2 % in the High treatment groups.

3.3. Microbial community composition of rearing water

Microbial alpha-diversity (within-group diversity) was assessed using four indices: The ACE index (Abundance-based Coverage Estimator) was applied to estimate taxon richness, with higher values indicating a greater number of detected taxa. The OTU index (Operational Taxonomic Unit) represented the number of identified taxa, determined by the presence of distinct DNA sequences. Shannon's diversity index quantified both richness and evenness, with higher values reflecting greater diversity, whereas Simpson's diversity index measured the probability that two randomly selected individuals belonged to the same taxon, with values approaching 1 indicating low diversity and values near 0 indicating high diversity. All four indices (ACE, OTU, Shannon's, and Simpson's) showed significant negative regressions ($P < 0.05$) with increasing O₃NB treatment levels (Fig. 2).

Fig. 1. The size (nm) and concentration of particles (bubbles in mL) in water: A – maximally saturated with ozone nanobubbles (generated by a nanobubble generator aQua+ 075, AquaPro Solutions Pte. Ltd., Singapore) and B – in tap water (blank sample without ozone nanobubbles) were measured using the nanoparticle tracking analysis (NanoSight NS300, Malvern Instruments Ltd., UK).

These relationships were best described by negative linear models: ACE ($P = 0.006$, adjusted $R^2 = 0.60$), OTU ($P = 0.006$, adjusted $R^2 = 0.59$), Shannon's ($P = 0.003$, adjusted $R^2 = 0.64$); and Simpson's ($P = 0.003$, adjusted $R^2 = 0.65$). Although microbial alpha-diversity did not differ significantly ($P > 0.05$) among the experimental groups (Fig. 3), a declining trend was evident with increasing O₃NB intensity, with the highest values in untreated pond water and the lowest under maximally O₃NB-saturated reservoir water, while only alpha-diversity values in the High O₃NB group partially overlapped with those of the source pond water samples. Rarefaction analysis indicated sufficient sequencing depth across samples, with Shannon diversity index curves approaching asymptotic plateaus across treatments (Suppl. 3 and 4).

To assess between-group variation, beta-diversity was evaluated using PCoA. It revealed distinct clustering of microbial community composition according to O₃NB treatment intensity (Fig. 4). PERMANOVA ($F = 4.37$, $R^2 = 0.785$, $P = 0.005$) and ANOSIM ($R^2 = 0.583$, $P = 0.004$) confirmed significant compositional differences among treatments. Overall, these results show that while microbial richness and

evenness declined with increasing O₃NB levels, the community structure also shifted markedly, reflecting a dose-dependent response.

The diversity of microorganisms, assessed at the phylum, family, and genus levels, differed partially between the tested O₃NB treatments. Across all water samples, microbial communities comprised 6 phyla, 18 families, and 22 genera (Fig. 4–5, Suppl. 5–9). The microbiota composition of the pond water supply (without O₃NB treatment) was characterised predominantly by the genera *Moheibacter* (11.8 %), *Limnohabitans* (11.6 %), and *Flavobacterium* (11.4 %), with other genera each accounting for <10 %. In contrast, the water subjected to the maximum O₃NB treatment exhibited a substantial reduction in genus richness, and the microbiota was dominated by *Moheibacter* (23.6 %), *Tepidimonas* (12.7 %), and *Sphingobacterium* (11.9 %), while all other genera were present at <10 %.

3.4. Hatching rate

Hatching of rainbow trout (%, Fig. 6) commenced at 47 days post-

Fig. 2. The correlation between the alpha-diversity indices (ACE, OTU, Shannon's, and Simpson's) and different O₃NB concentrations (0 % – Control, 25 % – Low, 50 % – Moderate, 75 % – High, and 100 % – Ozonated pond water (reservoir)) using linear regression with confidence intervals.

Fig. 3. The alpha-diversity of microorganisms (assessed through microbiology indices – ACE, OTU, Shannon's, and Simpson's) in rearing pond water with different O₃NB treatments: Control, Low, Moderate, High, Ozonated pond water (reservoir), and Pond water (reservoir).

fertilisation (dpF) in most groups (Control-NR, Low-NR, Moderate-NR, Moderate-R, and High-R). Significant differences ($P < 0.05$, two-way ANOVA) among groups became evident between 50 and 63 dpF. Overall, the hatching rate was significantly affected ($P < 0.05$, two-way ANOVA) by both rearing technique (NR vs. R) and the four O₃NB treatments (Control–High). On average, the R-technique improved hatching by approximately one-third compared with the NR-technique. Hatching success decreased progressively with increasing O₃NB concentration. Across experimental days 47–63 dpF, hatching rates also differed significantly ($P < 0.05$, two-way ANOVA), with a rapid increase from 5 % to 54 % between 50 and 56 dpF. A significant interaction effect ($P < 0.05$, two-way ANOVA) was detected between rearing technique and O₃NB treatment.

By the end of hatching (63 dpF), the highest rates (~80 %) were recorded in groups Control-R, Low-R, and Moderate-R, followed by

Control-NR and Low-NR (65–75 %). Significantly lower rates (<40 %) occurred in groups High-R and Moderate-NR, while the lowest value (<5 %) was observed in group High-NR. These differences among groups ($P < 0.05$) were confirmed by one-way ANOVA.

3.5. Yolk-sac absorption

Yolk-sac volume of rainbow trout (mm³, Fig. 7) was not significantly influenced ($P > 0.05$, two-way ANOVA) by the two rearing techniques (NR and R). In contrast, the four O₃NB treatments (Control–High) had a significant effect ($P < 0.05$, two-way ANOVA). On average, the mean yolk-sac volume was largest in the Control group and decreased with increasing O₃NB concentration, reaching its lowest values in the Low group, while the Moderate and High groups did not differ significantly from each other. Overall, yolk-sac volume differed significantly ($P <$

Fig. 4. Principal coordinates analysis (PCoA) based on Bray–Curtis dissimilarity illustrating differences in microbial community composition of rearing pond water under various O₃NB treatments: Control, Low, Moderate, High, Ozonated pond water (reservoir), and Pond water (reservoir). Statistical significance of compositional differences was confirmed by PERMANOVA ($F = 4.37$, $R^2 = 0.785$, $P = 0.002$) and ANOSIM ($R^2 = 0.583$, $P = 0.004$).

Fig. 5. Mean relative abundance (%) of the microbial community (top 20 genera) in rearing pond water with different O₃NB treatments: Control, Low, Moderate, High, Ozonated pond water (reservoir), and Pond water (reservoir).

0.05, two-way ANOVA) across experimental days, decreasing from 86.6 to 53.5 mm³ between 56–63 dpF, and further to 18.0 mm³ at 70 dpF. By 77 dpF, no yolk remained in any fish. No interaction effect ($P > 0.05$, two-way ANOVA) was observed between rearing technique and O₃NB treatment.

At hatching, yolk-sac volume was greatest in the Control group and decreased with increasing O₃NB concentration (Control–High). By 63 dpF, the largest yolk-sac was observed in the Control-R group, while other groups (Control-NR, Low-NR, Low-R, Moderate-NR, Moderate-R, and High-R) had significantly smaller volumes. No fish survived in the High-NR group at this stage. By 70 dpF, yolk-sac volume no longer differed significantly between groups, and by 77 dpF, no residual yolk was present. These differences among groups ($P < 0.05$) were confirmed by one-way ANOVA.

3.6. Growth performance

The total body length of rainbow trout (mm, Fig. 8) was significantly influenced ($P < 0.05$, two-way ANOVA) by both rearing technique (NR and R) and the four O₃NB treatments (Control–High) in this study. On average, the R-technique resulted in greater body length compared with the NR-technique. Mean body length was greatest in the Low treatment, whereas the shortest lengths were observed in the Moderate and High treatments; the Control group did not differ significantly from these. Body length also varied significantly ($P < 0.05$, two-way ANOVA) across experimental days, increasing from 17.4 mm to 21.6 mm between 56 and 63 dpF, and reaching 25.0 mm by 70 dpF. A significant interaction effect ($P < 0.05$, two-way ANOVA) between rearing technique and O₃NB treatment was also detected.

At hatching, fish were longest in groups Low-R and Moderate-NR, and shortest in Low-NR, while the remaining groups (Control-NR, Control-R, Moderate-R, High-NR, and High-R) did not differ

Fig. 6. The *O. mykiss* hatching rate (% of stocked eggs, mean ± SD) in eight tested groups (Control-R, Control-NR, Low-R, Low-NR, Moderate-R, Moderate-NR, High-R, and High-NR) at 47–63 days post fertilisation. If the *P*-level of significance was less than 0.05, the upper superscripts indicated differences between groups (a-d, Tukey's HSD test).

Fig. 7. The *O. mykiss* yolk-sac volume (mm³, mean ± SD) in eight tested groups (Control-R, Control-NR, Low-R, Low-NR, Moderate-R, Moderate-NR, High-R, and High-NR) at 56–70 days post fertilisation. If the *P*-level of significance was less than 0.05, the upper superscripts indicated differences between groups (a-b, Tukey's HSD test).

significantly. By 63 dpF, the longest body lengths remained in Low-R and the shortest in High-R (except for High-NR, where no fish survived in the sampling incubator). The other groups (Control-NR, Control-R, Low-NR, Moderate-NR, and Moderate-R) did not show significant differences. By the end of the study (70 dpF), body length was still greatest in Low-R and shortest in Moderate-NR, while the other groups (Control-NR, Control-R, Low-NR, and Moderate-R) showed no significant differences. These differences among groups (*P* < 0.05) were confirmed by one-way ANOVA.

3.7. Survival rate

The survival rate of rainbow trout (%, Fig. 9) was significantly influenced (*P* < 0.05, two-way ANOVA) by both rearing technique (NR and R) and the four O₃NB treatments (Control-High). On average, the R-technique improved survival by approximately one-third compared with the NR-treatment. Survival decreased progressively with increasing O₃NB concentration. Survival also differed significantly (*P* < 0.05, two-way ANOVA) across experimental days, declining from 85 % to 60 % at 33–50 dpF, and further to 42–33 % at 65–70 dpF. And a significant interaction effect (*P* < 0.05) between rearing technique (NR and R) and O₃NB treatment (Low-High) was also detected by two-way ANOVA.

Fig. 8. The *O. mykiss* total body length (mm, mean \pm SD) in eight tested groups (Control-R, Control-NR, Low-R, Low-NR, Moderate-R, Moderate-NR, High-R, and High-NR) at 56–70 days post fertilisation. If the *P*-level of significance was less than 0.05, the upper superscripts indicated differences between groups (a-d, Tukey's HSD test).

Fig. 9. The *O. mykiss* survival rate (% of stocked eggs, mean \pm SD) in eight tested groups (Control-R, Control-NR, Low-R, Low-NR, Moderate-R, Moderate-NR, High-R, and High-NR) at 33–70 days post fertilisation. If the *P*-level of significance was less than 0.05, the upper superscripts indicated differences between groups (a-d, Tukey's HSD test).

By the end of the trial (70 dpF), the highest survival rates ($\sim 60\%$) were recorded in groups Control-NR and Control-R, followed by groups Low-NR and Moderate-R ($\sim 40\%$). Group Moderate-NR showed a significantly lower survival ($\sim 10\%$), while the lowest values ($< 5\%$) were observed in groups High-NR/High-R. These differences among groups ($P < 0.05$) were confirmed by one-way ANOVA.

4. Discussion

4.1. Particle size distribution and concentration

Nanoparticle tracking analysis confirmed that O_3NB generation reduced bubble size and increased bubble density compared with

untreated water. The O_3NB -treated water had a mean bubble size of 136 nm and a concentration of $\sim 1.5e^{08} \text{ mL}^{-1}$, nearly an order of magnitude higher than the untreated control (260 nm; $\sim 1.7e^{07} \text{ mL}^{-1}$). According to [51], gas bubbles < 1000 nm in both liquids and solids are generally classified as ultrafine bubbles (nanobubbles), placing the bubbles produced here well within the recognised range. Comparable dimensions (100–200 nm) are widely reported in aquaculture and environmental applications, confirming the generation of stable nanobubbles with extended gas retention and high oxidative capacity (< 200 nm, [52]; 169 nm, [53]; 200 nm, [30]; 168 nm, [32]).

4.2. Microbial community characteristics of rearing water

Microbial community composition and structure play a crucial role in maintaining aquaculture water quality and fish health, underpinning nutrient cycling, organic matter degradation, and host–microbe interactions [54,55]. In this study, all four diversity indices (ACE, OTU, Shannon, and Simpson) showed a significant negative relationship with increasing O₃NB intensity, indicating reduced bacterial community richness and evenness under stronger oxidative exposure. Although alpha-diversity did not differ statistically among treatments, the overall trend towards lower values with increasing O₃NB levels suggests that intense O₃ application may constrain community heterogeneity and alter microbial community structure. The only exception was the High O₃NB treatment, which showed partial similarity to the source pond water; this pattern may reflect non-linear responses under extreme oxidative conditions or a potential experimental artefact, and results from the High treatment should therefore be interpreted cautiously. Nevertheless, the overall trend supports that increasing oxidative pressure can influence microbial community structure, with potential implications for ecological resilience [56,42]. Importantly, high microbial diversity does not necessarily equate to better system health, as reduced diversity resulting from pathogen or opportunist suppression may be advantageous under certain rearing conditions.

Beta-diversity analysis revealed clustering of microbial communities by O₃NB treatment, confirming significant differences in community composition among treatments. These patterns are consistent with selective effects of O₃-based oxidation, whereby taxa commonly associated with organic-rich freshwater environments and potential opportunists (e.g. *Limnohabitans* and *Flavobacterium*) were reduced, while O₃-tolerant genera such as *Moheibacter*, *Tepidimonas*, and *Sphingobacterium* increased in relative abundance under higher O₃NB exposure. Such shifts align with previous studies demonstrating that O₃-based disinfection selectively suppresses O₃-sensitive taxa while favouring more resistant microbial groups [38,57,58]. For instance, Huang et al. [86] found that O₃NB treatments reduced dominant bacterial taxa while increasing heterotrophic bacterial counts compared with air microbubbles, and Trang et al. [32] likewise reported the suppression of dominant taxa at elevated O₃NB dosing. Consistent with these microbial shifts, Guo et al. [59] showed that O₂NB treatment can also reduce pathogenic microorganisms in water, highlighting the potential of NB-based oxidation to manage microbial load and community structure in aquaculture systems.

Taxonomic profiling further revealed that untreated pond water contained diverse genera, including *Moheibacter*, *Limnohabitans*, and *Flavobacterium*, typical of freshwater systems and associated with organic matter turnover [36,60,86]. Under maximum O₃NB exposure, however, genus richness was markedly reduced, and the community became dominated by O₃-resistant taxa, such as *Moheibacter*, *Tepidimonas*, and *Sphingobacterium*. While such restructuring may contribute to suppression of opportunistic or potentially pathogenic bacteria [27, 21,30], it may also reduce the presence of beneficial or functionally important microbes, potentially undermining long-term ecosystem stability and fish performance [38,41,42,57,86]. Accordingly, microbial community composition alone is not a definitive indicator of system health, as reduced diversity associated with pathogen suppression may, in some cases, be advantageous in hatchery environments.

Studies using other NB-systems show similar but sometimes beneficial alterations to microbial balance; for example, nano-aerators increased the abundance of beneficial taxa such as *Exiguobacterium* and *Acinetobacter* in rearing water and promoted gut-associated genera (*Faecalibacterium* and *Rhodobacter*) in shrimps (*P. vannamei*) [36], while O₂NB shifted community structure in Nile tilapia [61]. Conversely, Dahle et al. [56] and Teitge et al. [57] found that O₃-disinfected water yielded less diverse and potentially less stable microbial communities than untreated controls. Overall, these findings suggest that low to moderate O₃NB exposure can reshape microbial communities by

reducing opportunistic and pathogenic taxa while preserving key functional groups, highlighting the importance of functional community composition over diversity alone for sustainable hatchery management and reduced reliance on antibiotics use in aquaculture [27,86].

It is worth noting that 16S rRNA gene sequencing does not distinguish between live, inactive, or dead bacterial cells [86]. As water samples were collected from the water column rather than the tank bottom, O₃-induced cell lysis and subsequent sedimentation of dead or lysed bacterial cells may have contributed to their underrepresentation in the sequencing dataset, potentially influencing the interpretation of microbial viability and activity [62,63].

4.3. Chemical stress sensitivity

Rainbow trout is a highly sensitive species to chemical stressors, including oxidising agents, metals, and other waterborne contaminants, which can disrupt metabolic and antioxidant pathways and affect stress- and immune-related responses, as shown by transcriptomic and physiological studies [64–66]. In this study, periodic increases in dissolved O₂ and ORP associated with O₃NB operation may represent a form of chemical or oxidative stress, particularly at higher treatment intensities, as O₃ and O₃-derived oxidants are known to induce oxidative and inflammatory responses in salmonids under elevated or continuous exposure [64,67,68]. Although physiological stress indicators were not assessed, the reduced survival and performance observed at higher O₃NB exposure may indicate that oxidative conditions approached the tolerance limits of early life stages, with implications for hatching success, growth performance, and survival discussed below.

4.4. Hatching rate

Hatching success in fish is highly sensitive to incubation practices and water quality [69,8]. In this study, the regular removal of unfertilized eggs and dead individuals (R-technique) significantly improved hatching rates, likely by reducing organic substrates that facilitate fungal and microbial proliferation. *Saprolegnia* spp., for example, are known to degrade the chorionic membrane of fish eggs, initially colonising unfertilised or dead eggs before spreading to viable embryos, often causing substantial mortality [70–72]. Without effective hygiene or disinfection, such infections can rapidly compromise egg viability and overall hatching performance in hatchery systems [73,70].

Without the removal of dead organic matter (NR-technique), O₃NB treatment alone resulted in lower hatching success, likely because retained organic material continued to serve as a substrate for fungal and microbial growth. Increased oxidative activity associated with O₃NB exposure may further facilitate the spread of opportunistic egg-associated pathogens from dead to viable eggs, thereby overwhelming the antimicrobial benefits of ozonation. These findings highlight that O₃NB cannot substitute for physical removal of organic matter but must be applied alongside standard hatchery hygiene practices. Accordingly, the benefits of the R-technique were most evident in the Low and Moderate O₃NB groups, where hatching approached ~80 %, underscoring that O₃NB functions as a supportive rather than substitutive measure. In contrast, the High O₃NB group markedly reduced hatching (<5 % in the High-NR group), consistent with previous evidence that excessive O₃ can impair embryonic development via oxidative stress and membrane damage [45,74,32].

Experimental studies with other species corroborate these results. Grotmol et al. [44] found that low ozone exposures (below 2 mg L⁻¹) maintained normal hatching success, whereas higher doses reduced viability of Atlantic halibut (*Hippoglossus hippoglossus*), Atlantic cod (*Gadus morhua*) and turbot (*Scophthalmus maximus*) eggs. Likewise, Ghomi et al. [75] reported improved hatching (76.4 %) in ozone-treated (0.15 ppm) Iranian sturgeon (*Acipenser persicus*) eggs compared with untreated controls without infected egg removal (34.4 %). Conversely, Fry et al. [43] observed no significant effects of low–high ozonation

(0.5–3.0 mg L⁻¹) on rainbow trout and Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar*) hatching (73–85 %), highlighting species-specific ozone tolerance. Collectively, these findings indicate that moderate O₃NB dosing, combined with good husbandry practices such as removing infected eggs, can support successful hatching, whereas excessive oxidative exposure compromises embryonic development.

4.5. Yolk-sac absorption

Yolk-sac absorption underpins the transition from endogenous to exogenous feeding, providing essential energy for early growth and organogenesis [76,77]. In this study, yolk-sac volume declined progressively with age, with complete absorption by 77 dpF, indicating readiness for external feeding. Although rearing technique (NR vs R) had no significant effect, O₃NB exposure significantly influenced yolk-sac dynamics. The largest yolk reserves were observed in the Control group, while reductions were most pronounced under Low O₃NB exposure, suggesting that oxidative conditions may accelerate yolk utilisation, potentially through increased metabolic demand or altered enzyme activity [59]. By 70 dpF, group differences had diminished, but early depletion under O₃NB could influence energy allocation and later larval performance.

Previous work has shown that moderate ozonation does not impair yolk utilisation or larval development. For instance, Fry et al. [43] found no adverse effects of ozone treatment (0.5–3.0 mg L⁻¹) on yolk-sac volume in rainbow trout and Atlantic salmon larvae. Our findings, therefore, suggest that moderate, well-controlled O₃NB exposure is compatible with normal yolk-sac absorption and early development, whereas higher oxidative levels may accelerate yolk depletion and reduce energy reserves. Balancing antibacterial efficacy with metabolic cost is thus essential for the use of O₃NB in fish hatcheries.

4.6. Growth performance

Body length trajectories in fish are determined by both genetic and environmental factors, including oxygenation, microbial load, and rearing conditions [78,75,8]. In this study, both rearing techniques and O₃NB treatments significantly influenced growth. The R-technique consistently promoted greater body length, likely due to reduced microbial stress resulting from the removal of dead material. Among O₃NB treatments, larvae in the Low group attained the greatest body lengths, whereas growth was suppressed in the Moderate and High exposures, consistent with potential oxidative stress at elevated ozone levels [79, 74]. Trang et al. [32] similarly reported that low to moderate O₃NB improved fish performance, whereas higher concentrations caused stress and performance loss. Binh et al. [53] demonstrated that shrimp (*P. vannamei*) exposed to O₃NB (0.3 mg L⁻¹) exhibited higher weights than controls, attributing the improvements to microbial modulation and enhanced water quality. Supporting this, Guo et al. [59] found that prolonged hyperoxia (~16 mg L⁻¹) from O₂NB exposure enhanced growth, digestive enzyme activity, and antioxidant capacity in kuruma shrimp (*Penaeus japonicus*), while improving water quality and reducing pathogen load. Collectively, these studies suggest that improved oxygenation, microbial modulation, and antioxidant defence act synergistically to enhance growth under moderate nanobubble treatment.

Stage-specific patterns further supported these results: at hatching, fish from Low-R and Moderate-NR were longest, while by 63 dpF, Low-R remained superior and High-R markedly reduced growth. By 70 dpF, Low-R fish again exhibited the greatest length, indicating that early advantages under optimal O₃NB dosing and regular cleaning may persist throughout development. These findings agree with earlier reports that low-level ozone application supports fish performance, whereas excessive exposure impairs growth [44]. Growth promotion in Low-R coincides with studies showing that O₃NB elevates dissolved oxygen, improving water quality and survival [53,28,61]. Conversely, Li et al. [79] observed reduced growth, feed intake, conversion efficiency, and

altered haematology in European seabass (*Dicentrarchus labrax*) reared at more than 300 mV in recirculating systems. However, resistance to bacterial infection improved, implying that moderate oxidative exposure can enhance immune responsiveness despite metabolic costs. Together, these findings underscore the dual role of O₃NB: when carefully managed, it can optimise oxygen and microbial conditions, but excessive exposure can impose physiological stress. Dose-dependent application, combined with sound hatchery management, is therefore crucial for maximising growth potential.

4.7. Survival rate

Survival was strongly influenced by husbandry, with the regular removal of mortalities improving outcomes by approximately one-third compared with the NR-technique. This aligns with previous work showing that effective egg management reduces fungal infection and microbial stress, thereby improving larval performance [73,75,80]. The benefits of the R-technique were most evident in the Control, Low, and Moderate O₃NB groups, where final survival yielded ~40–60 %. Such ranges are typical of pond-water hatcheries, where natural variations in temperature, oxygen, and microbial load often result in lower survival rates than in controlled-flow-through or recirculating systems. This contrast emphasises the need for selective disinfection to protect early life stages in pond-water systems.

Survival declined progressively with O₃NB intensity, reaching the lowest values (<5 %) in the High treatment (~610 mV). This supports warnings that prolonged oxidative stress above can damage the gill and embryonic tissue, causing mortality [79,19,32]. Trang et al. [32] also found that applying low O₃NB doses (0.5 mg L⁻¹) during the embryo stage and O₂NB during the fry stage improved survival and hatching in common carp (*Cyprinus carpio*). In the present study, the Low (~277 mV) and Moderate (~392 mV) treatments yielded intermediate survival rates, reflecting the need to balance antimicrobial efficacy with physiological safety. Similar dose-dependent trends have been reported in other species: Grotmol & Totland [45] observed higher survival in Atlantic halibut exposed to low ozone treatment (1–4 mg L⁻¹) than in controls, with no adverse effects on larval development, while Fry et al. [43] reported reduced survival in rainbow trout (74–75 %) at ozonation (0.5–3.0 mg L⁻¹) compared to the controls (82 %), but Atlantic salmon survival was not affected by ozonation. Together, these findings indicate that O₃NB can be used effectively as a supportive intervention alongside good husbandry practices (rather than as a replacement), provided exposure is tightly controlled to minimise oxidative stress.

4.8. System-specific considerations for the O₃NB technology

It is also important to note that the applicability of NB technologies can be influenced by production system design. Raceway systems, the most common culture method for rainbow trout, have high water exchange rates, which can limit NB retention and may favour the use of O₃NB as a targeted or intermittent treatment (e.g. in reservoirs or side-stream units) rather than continuous in-line application [81,68]. In contrast, recirculating aquaculture systems (RAS), including aquaponics, provide more controlled hydraulics and longer retention, potentially enabling more precise regulation of O₂, O₃, and ORP conditions [82–84]. However, in RAS and aquaponics, O₃NB application requires careful management to minimise unintended impacts on beneficial microbial communities, particularly nitrifying biofilms and plant-associated microbiota, as oxidant carry-over may impair nitrogen transformation processes [85,20]. Overall, the effectiveness of NB technologies, including optimal dosing and operational integration, is likely to be system-specific and should therefore be evaluated on a case-by-case basis.

5. Conclusions

This study shows that ozone nanobubble (O₃NB) technology, when applied at low to moderate levels and used to complement (rather than replace) routine husbandry practices, such as the regular removal of dead organic matter, can improve early developmental performance of rainbow trout and alter microbial community composition in hatchery systems with elevated organic load in the water. In contrast, high O₃NB exposure consistently reduced hatching, growth, and survival, likely reflecting oxidative stress and disruption of microbial balance. These findings indicate that careful dose optimisation is essential: at appropriate levels, O₃NB can function as a supportive management tool alongside good husbandry practices, whereas excessive exposure poses clear risks to embryo and larval viability. When appropriately controlled, O₃NB has the potential to enhance biosecurity and sustainability in aquaculture.

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Originality

We confirm that the manuscript is original and has not been published previously, in whole or in part, and is not currently under consideration for publication elsewhere. All authors have been properly credited for their contributions.

Declaration of generative AI technologies in the manuscript preparation process

During the preparation of this work, the authors used a generative AI tool (ChatGPT v. 5.2) to improve the English language and grammar. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Markéta Dvořáková Prokešová: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Hung Quang Tran:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Formal analysis. **Ilario Ferruccio:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Vlastimil Stejskal:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Maksim Kononov:** Investigation. **Vu Thi Trang:** Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis. **Pham Thai Giang:** Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis. **Elayaraja Sivaramasamy:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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